

Data Curation Log Template

1. Data Curation Workflow

Data curation can be defined as the diligent management of data from inception to ensure its future accessibility, reliability, and reusability, data curation forms the foundation of scientific integrity and the perpetuation of knowledge. Below is a tool to help data curators to gauge the level of maturity of data curation in their organization based on the data curation workflow in figure 1 below.

Figure 1 Generic Data Curation Workflow

1. Scoring Guidelines

The cumulative scores from each CURATE(D) focus areas and the FAIR principles detailed assessment are used to determine the dataset's maturity level within the DCMM framework. The scoring thresholds for maturity levels can be defined in the following thresholds:

- a) Initial (Ad Hoc): 0-13 points

At this level, data curation practices are undeveloped or inconsistently applied. There's a lack of formal policies or standards, and any existing practices are ad hoc and not systematically managed.

b) Managed (Repeatable): 14-26 points

Basic data curation policies are developed at this stage. Data management tasks are performed to some extent but might not be fully standardized or documented. There's an awareness of data curation needs, and initial steps towards structured practices are taken.

c) Defined (Standardized): 27-39 points

Comprehensive data curation policies and procedures are documented and communicated. There's a standard approach to data curation that's uniformly applied across projects, indicating a mature understanding and implementation of data management practices.

d) Quantitatively Managed (Measured): 40-52 points

Data curation processes are measured and controlled. Quantitative quality goals are set for data management, and performance is systematically tracked against these goals. This level signifies a sophisticated approach to data curation, with metrics and measurements guiding continuous improvement.

e) Optimizing (Continuously Improving): 53-66 points

The highest maturity level focuses on continuous improvement based on feedback from data curation practices and innovation. Data curation processes are regularly reviewed and updated for efficacy and efficiency, incorporating new tools and techniques. This level represents an advanced state of data curation maturity, where practices are not only standardized and measured but are also subject to ongoing optimization and refinement.

2. Scoring Template

Project and Dataset Overview

- Project Title:
- Principal Investigator(s):
- Data Curator(s):

- Dataset Title(s):
- Date Range of Data Collection:
- Funding Source(s) and Grant Number(s):
- Target Repository for Data Deposit:
- DCMM Initial Assessment Level:

CURATE(D) Process Documentation and Scoring

Each CURATE(D) step includes specific activities that are scored on a scale (0-2: 0 = Not Done, 1 = Partially Done, 2 = Fully Done). The cumulative score from each section contributes to determining the dataset's maturity level.

1. CHECK Step: Initial Review and Inventory

Activity	Details	Date	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
Inventory Completion				
Documentation Review				
Ethical Considerations Assessment				
Scope and Relevance for Repository				

Total CHECK Score: /8

2. UNDERSTAND Step: Data Examination

Activity	Details	Date	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
Quality Assurance Checks				
Usability and Documentation Sufficiency				
Hidden Documentation Extraction				

Total UNDERSTAND Score: /6

3. REQUEST Step: Communication with Data Creators

Activity	Details	Date	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
Missing Information Requests				
Changes Requested for Data Usability				
Ethical Concerns Addressed				

Total REQUEST Score: /6

4. AUGMENT Step: Metadata and Documentation Enhancement

Activity	Details	Date	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
Metadata Enhancement for Discoverability				
Documentation Improvement for Reuse				
Domain-Specific Schema Implementation				

Total AUGMENT Score: /6

5. TRANSFORM Step: File Format Conversion

Activity	Details	Date	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
Identification of Specialized Formats				
Conversion to Open/Reusable Formats				
Retention of Original Formats				

Total TRANSFORM Score: /6

6. EVALUATE Step: FAIR Principles Detailed Assessment

Each FAIR principle is assessed with specific criteria, scored on a scale of 0-2. The cumulative score for each principle contributes to the overall FAIR alignment score.

a) Findable

Criteria	Evaluation/Notes	Date	Actions Required	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier					
F2. Data are described with rich metadata					
F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes					
F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource					

Findable Score: /8

b) Accessible

Criteria	Evaluation/Notes	Date	Actions Required	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized					

communications protocol					
A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable					
A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary					
A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available					

Accessible Score: /8

c) Interoperable

Criteria	Evaluation/Notes	Date	Actions Required	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation					

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles					
I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data					

Interoperable Score: /6

d) Reusable

Criteria	Evaluation/Notes	Date	Actions Required	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
R1. Meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes					
R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license					
R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance					
R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards					

Interoperable Score: /6

Total EVALUATE Score: /30

7. DOCUMENT Step: Final Curation Record

Activity	Details	Date	Curator Initials	Score (0-2)
Final Review and Documentation				
Communication with Data Creators				
Submission to Target Repository				

Total DOCUMENT Score: /6

Total Maturity Score: /66